

The Effect of Extensive Reading Courses on Vocabulary Improvement in ELED Students

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ABSTRAK

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengetahui pengaruh penerapan metode Extensive Reading terhadap peningkatan penguasaan kosakata bahasa Inggris pada siswa kelas tujuh di SMP Negeri 12 Sipatana. Penguasaan kosakata merupakan aspek penting dari keterampilan berbahasa Inggris, yang mendasari kemampuan membaca, menulis, berbicara, dan mendengarkan. Metode Extensive Reading dinilai efektif karena memberikan masukan bahasa yang luas dan kontekstual melalui kegiatan membaca bebas yang menyenangkan dan sesuai dengan minat siswa. Penelitian ini menggunakan pendekatan kuantitatif dengan desain pra-eksperimental tipe one group pre-test and post-test. Sampel dalam penelitian ini terdiri dari 23 siswa kelas tujuh yang dipilih melalui purposive sampling. Instrumen penelitian adalah tes pilihan ganda yang terdiri dari 50 pertanyaan yang mencakup empat jenis kata (kata benda, kata kerja, kata sifat, dan kata keterangan). Data dianalisis menggunakan uji-t sampel berpasangan melalui program SPSS versi 23. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan adanya peningkatan yang signifikan pada skor rata-rata post-test (60,30) dibandingkan dengan pre-test (56,47). Uji statistik menunjukkan nilai signifikansi $0,000 < 0,05$, yang berarti H_0 ditolak dan H_a diterima. Dengan demikian, dapat

disimpulkan bahwa metode Membaca Ekstensif berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap peningkatan penguasaan kosakata siswa. Temuan ini mendukung bahwa Membaca Ekstensif dapat menjadi strategi pembelajaran alternatif yang efektif untuk meningkatkan motivasi dan keterampilan kosakata siswa dalam pembelajaran bahasa Inggris di tingkat SMP.

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of applying the Extensive Reading method on improving English vocabulary mastery among seventh-grade students at SMP Negeri 12 Sipatana. Vocabulary mastery is an important aspect of English language skills, which underlies the ability to read, write, speak, and listen. The Extensive Reading method is considered effective because it provides broad and contextual language input through enjoyable free reading activities that are in line with students' interests. This study used a quantitative approach with a pre-experimental design of the one group pre-test and post-test type. The sample in this study consisted of 23 seventh-grade students selected through purposive sampling. The research instrument was a multiple-choice test consisting of 50 questions covering four parts of speech (nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs). The data were analyzed using a paired sample t-test through the SPSS version 23 program. The results showed a significant increase in the post-test average score (60.30) compared to the pre-test (56.47). The statistical test showed a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, which means H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. Thus, it can be concluded that the Extensive Reading method has a positive and significant effect on improving students' vocabulary mastery. These findings support that Extensive Reading can be an effective alternative learning strategy to increase students' motivation and vocabulary skills in English learning at the junior high school level.

INTRODUCTION

As an international language, English is the most important language to learn and plays a significant role in global communication. Mastering English makes it easier for us to communicate with people abroad and also helps people apply for and obtain better jobs on an international scale. Therefore, English is taught in almost all schools in Indonesia, from elementary school to college.

English consists of four skills, one of which is reading. Reading is defined as the process by which readers seek to acquire new knowledge and information by reading newspapers, books, magazines, articles, or even journals. In other words, reading is a way to obtain information through written text. By reading,

students can access a wealth of information that may not otherwise be available, especially English textbooks for Indonesians who love to read. In addition, the Indonesian public's view of reading is largely wrong. They assume that reading is a boring and tedious activity that is difficult to do, when in fact reading can be fun, simple, and easy to do. (Dondian Putra et al., 2019).

(Vaughn & Stevens, 2024) argues that extensive reading is one of the most effective ways to increase vocabulary. In his "input hypothesis" theory, Krashen states that language acquisition occurs when learners are exposed to a large amount of comprehensible input, which is the essence of extensive reading. One method that has attracted the attention of educators and researchers is extensive reading.

Extensive reading is a type of reading where extensive reading means reading in quantity to gain a general understanding of what is being read. Extensive reading is an activity where students read several materials in another language, and they are free to choose the materials they want to read according to their ability level. This is intended to develop good reading habits to build vocabulary and knowledge of structure and encourage enjoyment. In an English as a foreign language environment, extensive reading is one of the alternative techniques for teaching reading and increasing students' interest in reading. Research shows that extensive reading has many positive effects and is considered one of the most effective activities for improving students' reading skills. However, when students are interested in and enjoy the texts they read, this can encourage them to read more and change their perception of reading from a boring activity to an enjoyable one where they can discover new knowledge and understanding about what they read.

In the context of English as a Foreign Language, there are several key skills that students need to master. If students do not master and possess English language skills, this will certainly have a major impact on the progress of the nation, causing it to lag behind in science and technology and unable to compete with other developed countries. Therefore, we need to learn and master several English language skills, including listening, speaking, writing, and reading. In relation to English language learning, there are four basic skills, namely reading, listening, writing, and speaking. These four skills are separate from one another, but they are interrelated and can even be combined with one another.

However, to master the above skills, students must have an adequate vocabulary. Vocabulary is very important to master because it will affect other English skills such as listening, reading, writing, and speaking. The richer the vocabulary, the greater the opportunity to be proficient in the language. However, if students do not master vocabulary, they will have difficulty understanding conversations and readings in English. In addition, they will also have difficulty communicating orally and in writing in English. Therefore, vocabulary mastery is the most important thing for having good English language skills.

Vocabulary refers to the collection of words in a particular language. Vocabulary learning contributes greatly to a person's ability to communicate in English (Murdy, 2015). In the context of English, vocabulary includes all words used in the language, including nouns and verbs, adjectives, adverbs, phrases, and idioms. English vocabulary consists of various levels, ranging from basic to advanced vocabulary. Vocabulary plays an important role in learning English, both at the basic and advanced levels. Furthermore, difficulties in vocabulary mastery among junior high school students can include errors in spelling, pronunciation, and word choice. These obstacles can arise in both writing and speaking skills. Several factors contribute to these problems, including low motivation to learn, difficulty concentrating during the learning process, the influence of the family environment, social dynamics in the school environment, and limited educational facilities and infrastructure. Therefore, this title describes an important research focus in junior high school education. As in the study conducted by Ying & Yanting (2021) entitled "The Effect of Extensive Reading on Reading Comprehension and Vocabulary Knowledge of EFL Mandarin Learners". This study investigated the effectiveness of extensive reading in improving reading comprehension and vocabulary mastery among English learners in China. The findings show that extensive reading has a positive and significant impact on improving both aspects.

Another study conducted by Rashidi & Piran (2021) entitled "The Effect of Extensive Reading versus Intensive Reading on Reading Comprehension and Vocabulary Knowledge of Iranian EFL Learners". This study compared the effectiveness of extensive reading and intensive reading in improving reading comprehension and vocabulary mastery. The results showed that extensive reading was proven to be more effective in improving reading comprehension and vocabulary mastery.

The last previous study by Shih (2020) was titled "The Effect of Extensive Reading on Vocabulary Acquisition and Reading Comprehension among EFL Learners." This study investigated the impact of extensive reading on vocabulary acquisition and reading comprehension among learners of English as a foreign language. The results showed that extensive reading plays an important role in improving learners' vocabulary mastery.

In English language learning, vocabulary mastery is one of the key factors that support students' language skills. Although the curriculum has established Descriptive Reading material in the learning modules at school, many students still have difficulty enriching their vocabulary. One of the reasons for this

is the lack of exposure to reading materials that are interesting and relevant to their interests. The lack of student engagement in reading also often leads to slow and limited vocabulary development.

To overcome this problem, researchers offer the application of extensive reading as a reading technique that can help students expand their vocabulary in a more natural and enjoyable way. Extensive reading encourages students to read a variety of texts according to their interests without excessive academic pressure. Several previous studies have proven the effectiveness of extensive reading in improving students' reading and vocabulary skills. For example, a study conducted by Nation (2001) shows that extensive reading-based learning can significantly improve text comprehension while enriching vocabulary. In addition, Renandya & Jacobs (2016) also emphasize that extensive reading not only increases vocabulary, but also improves students' attitudes toward reading and strengthens their understanding of language structure.

With this approach, it is hoped that students will be more motivated to read, thereby indirectly increasing their vocabulary. Through this study, extensive reading is expected to be an effective solution in increasing students' interest in reading and enriching their vocabulary, which will ultimately have a positive impact on their overall English language skills. This research design uses a quantitative method. Data was collected through pre-tests and post-tests for grade VII B students in the 2025/2026 academic year who participated in this study. The results of this study will show the extent of improvement in students' vocabulary after participating in the extensive reading treatment process.

Based on the background, the following research questions can be formulated: What is the effect of extensive reading on vocabulary improvement among seventh-grade students at SMP 12 Sipatana?.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses quantitative techniques because of the systematic measurement and quantification of variables. The collected numerical data were analyzed using IBM SPSS-21.

The population in this study was the students of class VII B in the 2025-2026 academic year at SMP 12 Sipatana. The researcher used Purposive Sampling, which only involved one class. The sample consisted of 23 students. The reason for selecting all students in class VII A as the research sample was to prepare them to master vocabulary.

Data collection was carried out using tests, the test used was a multiple-choice test with choices a, b, c and d consisting of Fourth types of vocabulary namely nouns, verbs and adjectives and Adverb contained in the Narrative text material. Researchers gave a tryout of 50 questions in the form of multiple choice to students. The instrument indicators in this study only focus on vocabulary such as nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. The test scheme is described in the table below.

In this research, the data analysis process involves several statistical techniques to evaluate the effectiveness of Extensive Reading in enhancing students' vocabulary mastery. To make things easier, researcher used SPSS Version 30.

RESULTS

Description of Pre-Test, Treatment, and Post-Test Data

Description of Pre-test Data

The pre-test was conducted by the researcher on students before they received the treatment. Before the researcher taught about extensive reading in improving students' vocabulary, the researcher collected pre-test data to determine students' abilities in extensive reading. The pre-test consisted of 30 multiple-choice questions, and the pre-test results showed that the highest scores of the students were as follows:

Pre-Test Graph

Source: Processed Data (2025)

The pre-test polygon graph illustrates the initial distribution of students' vocabulary abilities based on four main word classes, namely nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. The results show that the highest mastery was in the noun category (score of 97), followed by verbs (score of 75). Meanwhile, students' understanding of adjectives (score of 52) and especially adverbs (score of 39) was still relatively low. These findings indicate that before the learning intervention, students' vocabulary skills tended to be stronger in the more commonly used categories (nouns and verbs) but still weak in more complex categories such as adjectives and adverbs.

Table 1 Frequency Interval of Student Vocabulary Pre-test Data

NO	CLASS INTERVAL	ABSOLUTE FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	0-8	3	13
2	9,10	5	22
3	11,12	6	26
4	13,14	8	35
5	15	1	4
Total		23	100%

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on the pre-test results distribution table, it can be seen that most students are concentrated in the middle score category. A total of 3 students (13%) were in the 0–8 score range, indicating very low vocabulary mastery. Then there were 5 students (22%) with scores of 9–10, which were also still in the low category. The largest number is in the 11–12 score group, namely 6 students (26%), and 8 students (35%) achieved a score of 13–14. Meanwhile, only 1 student (4%) managed to obtain the highest score in the 15 interval (). This distribution pattern shows that the majority of students (61%) were in the 11–14 score range, so it can be concluded that the students' initial vocabulary skills before the intervention were in the moderate category, with very few students achieving a high level of proficiency. The group of students who scored in the moderate range (41-60) consisted of 4 students (17%). Only 2 students (9%) scored in the 61-80 range, and 2 other students (9%) scored high in the 81-100 range. This data shows that before the intervention was implemented, only about 18% of the total students demonstrated sufficient vocabulary mastery.

Treatment of Students

First Meeting

I entered class VII A of SMP 12 Sipatana with several English folk tale books. The 23 students were already seated at their desks. I opened the meeting by greeting them, then introducing myself and explaining that during the five meetings we would be reading English stories in a different way, namely through *extensive reading*. I told them that the purpose of this activity was to increase their vocabulary through reading.

After the introduction, I wrote about narrative text on the board. I explained the meaning of narrative text, its function, and its structure: *orientation, complication, resolution, and re-orientation*. I asked some of the students if they had ever heard stories such as *Cinderella* or *Snow White*. Several nodded and smiled immediately, indicating that they were familiar with these stories in Indonesian.

The researcher then divided the students into five groups. Since there were 23 students, four groups of five students and one group of three students were formed. The groups were formed by considering the balance between active and passive students so that the discussion would run evenly. Once the groups were formed, I called each group to choose a story title. Group 1 chose *Snow White*, group 2 chose *Cinderella*, group 3 chose *Sleeping Beauty*, group 4 chose *Beauty and the Beast*, and group 5 chose *Hansel and Gretel*. Since there was only one copy of each story available, I immediately distributed soft copies of the stories via the class WhatsApp group so that all group members could read the same story simultaneously on their mobile phones. Then I gave them a blank sheet of paper to note down any unfamiliar vocabulary or new words.

After that, I gave the following instructions:

"Please read your stories. If you find new words or words you don't understand, write them down in your notebooks. To find the meaning, you can use the dictionary I have provided on the front table. If you still have difficulty, you can ask me directly."

The students began reading. I saw some students seriously searching through the text on their phone screens, while others whispered to each other while pointing at certain words. Occasionally, a student would stand up to take a dictionary from the front table. For example, a member of group 2 opened

the dictionary to look up the meaning of the word *slipper*. There was also a student from group 3 who asked me directly:

"Miss, what does *spindle* mean?"

I explained the meaning, using hand gestures to help them visualize it.

I walked around the classroom, looking at the students' notes. From my observations, each group found about 20-25 new vocabulary words. Some of them are as follows:

- Group 1 (Snow White): *dwarf, wicked, poisoned, huntsman, disguise*
- Group 2 (Cinderella): *slipper, carriage, fairy godmother, stepmother, midnight*
- Group 3 (Sleeping Beauty): *spindle, curse, thorn, enchantment*
- Group 4 (Beauty and the Beast): *beast, merchant, enchanted, rose, castle*
- Group 5 (Hansel and Gretel): *breadcrumbs, witch, oven, cottage, escape*

I then asked the students to categorize the vocabulary they had written down into nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. Some students seemed confused about the difference between verbs and nouns, so I gave examples on the board for them to copy. After that, I asked them to make at least two simple sentences using the new words they had found.

After all the groups had finished, I asked them to mark the story structure according to their respective texts. Some were able to immediately point out the *orientation* section because the story clearly introduced the characters and setting, but I still needed to guide some students when looking for the *resolution* section.

Towards the end of the meeting, each group presented their work. They mentioned the new vocabulary they had discovered, read their sentences, and then explained the narrative structure of their chosen story. I paid attention to their expressions: some looked confident when they came forward, while others still read their notes in a low voice.

From my experience in this first meeting, the students seemed enthusiastic but still a little awkward. They were excited to discover new vocabulary, although some had difficulty distinguishing the meanings of words without the help of a dictionary. I saw that their strategies varied: some preferred to open the dictionary themselves, some asked me directly, and others discussed with their friends. The classroom atmosphere was quite lively with small discussions in each group. I thought the activity went well, although there were still some students who were passive and waited for their friends to explain.

I closed the meeting by asking them what new vocabulary they found most interesting. Several students answered *fairy godmother, poisoned, and castle*. I praised them, then reminded them that in the next meeting they would continue reading another story to enrich their vocabulary.

Second Meeting

I returned to class VII A at SMP 12 Sipatana for the second meeting. The atmosphere in the classroom felt more relaxed than during the first meeting. Several students greeted me first and seemed enthusiastic to continue the reading activity. I opened the meeting by reminding them of the purpose of this activity, which was to get them more accustomed to reading narrative texts in English and enrich their vocabulary.

Before reading, I briefly reviewed the material from the previous meeting. I rewrote the structure of a narrative text on the board: *orientation, complication, resolution, and re-orientation*. I asked the students if they still remembered these parts. Several immediately replied, "Orientation is the introduction of characters and places, Miss," which showed that their understanding was beginning to form.

After that, I divided them into the same groups as in the first meeting. This time, I gave each group the opportunity to choose a different story title from the collection of books that had been prepared. The groups' choices were:

- Group 1: *Rapunzel*
- Group 2: *The Frog Prince*
- Group 3: *Jack and the Beanstalk*
- Group 4: *The Little Mermaid*
- Group 5: *Pinocchio*

As before, since each title only has one hard copy, I once again shared the soft copy of the story via WhatsApp so that all group members could read it simultaneously without waiting for their turn.

I gave the same instructions as in the first meeting:

"Please read your stories together with your group. Don't forget to note down new vocabulary or words you don't understand. You can look up their meanings in the dictionary I've provided on the front table, or you can ask me directly if you're still having trouble."

The students immediately began reading. This time, they seemed more accustomed to the task. Some took out their dictionaries without being told, and others had already prepared notes from the start. As I walked around, I saw members of group 3 confused by the word *beanstalk*, then they discussed it before

finally opening their dictionaries. Group 4 asked about the meaning of the word *mermaid*, and I explained it with a quick drawing on the board so they could visualize it clearly. From my observations, each group found around 18–22 new vocabulary words. Some examples are as follows:

- Group 1 (Rapunzel): *tower, braid, witch, rescue, window*
- Group 2 (The Frog Prince): *crown, pond, promise, golden ball, palace*
- Group 3 (Jack and the Beanstalk): *beanstalk, giant, treasure, harp, axe*
- Group 4 (The Little Mermaid): *ocean, scales, voice, prince, sacrifice*
- Group 5 (Pinocchio): *puppet, nose, carpenter, donkey, truth*

After that, I asked them to group the vocabulary into nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. This time, I noticed that the students worked faster than in the first meeting. Although some of them still placed words incorrectly, they began to discuss how to correct them.

Then, I instructed them to make two simple sentences from the selected vocabulary. For example, group 1 wrote: *Rapunzel has long braids* and *The witch locked her in the tower*. I praised their efforts even though the sentence structure was not perfect, because the main goal was to try to use new vocabulary.

The next step was to identify the narrative structure of the stories they read. This time, the students seemed more fluent. Group 3 immediately wrote that *the orientation* of the story *Jack and the Beanstalk* was the introduction of Jack and his poor mother. Group 5 explained that *the complication* in *Pinocchio* was the lie that made his nose grow long. I saw that they were beginning to get used to understanding the concept of narrative structure.

At the end of the session, each group came forward to present their work. They read several sentences they had written and explained the story structure they had found. I noticed that more students dared to speak than in the first meeting, although some still looked nervous.

In this second meeting, I saw progress from the students. They seemed more confident in using the dictionary and asking questions directly if there were difficult words. Some students who tended to be passive in the first meeting now began to participate in group discussions. The classroom atmosphere became livelier with small bursts of laughter when they found strange words, such as when group 2 read the word *frog prince*. I believe that repeating the task from the first meeting greatly helped them understand the process of reading narrative texts while enriching their vocabulary.

I closed the meeting by giving appreciation to all groups and reminding them that the more they read, the more new vocabulary they can master.

Third Meeting

The third meeting began with me entering class VII A of SMP 12 Sipatana. The atmosphere seemed more familiar than the previous meeting. The students immediately greeted me, some even asking what story they would be reading today. I opened the activity by reminding them of two important things in *narrative text*: vocabulary and story structure.

Today, I explained that they would make a story map

Before starting to read, I wrote the definition of *a story map* on the board:

"A story map is a map of a story that contains descriptions of the characters, setting, problems, and solutions of a story. By making a story map, you can more easily understand the storyline and see the relationships between the parts of the text."

I drew a simple example on the board in the form of boxes:

- Characters
- Setting (setting: place and time)
- Problem/Conflict (problem/conflict)
- Events (important events, brief plot)
- Resolution (problem resolution)

I will explain the steps to create it:

1. Read the story carefully.
2. Note down all the characters that appear.
3. Determine the setting and time of the events (Setting).
4. Identify the main problem or conflict (Problem).
5. List the important events (Events).
6. Write down how the problem is resolved (Resolution).

I added that the benefit of a story map is that it helps them see the storyline visually so that it is easier to understand, and also trains them to find the *orientation*, *complication*, and *resolution* parts in narrative texts. After the explanation, I asked the five groups that had been divided earlier to come forward and choose the books they would read today. Each group chose a new story to read:

- Group 1: *Aladdin and the Magic Lamp*
- Group 2: *The Ugly Duckling*

- Group 3: *The Golden Goose*
- Group 4: *Peter Pan*
- Group 5: *The Emperor's New Clothes*

I shared the soft files to their phones so that all members could read them at the same time. I emphasized again:

"Please read your stories first. Write down new vocabulary words, then group them into word classes. After that, make a story map on the paper I have distributed. If you find a difficult word, you can use the dictionary on the front table or ask me directly."

The students began reading seriously. I walked around to monitor them. Group 1 seemed confused by the word *genie*, so they opened the dictionary. Group 5 chuckled when they read the word *invisible*, and they asked me what it meant. I explained that *invisible* means "not seen," then I gave an example by mentioning the character *Invisible Man*.

After reading, the students wrote down new vocabulary words. On average, each group found 20–28 new vocabulary words. Some examples:

- Aladdin: *genie, lamp, wish, palace, treasure*
- Ugly Duckling: *duckling, feathers, swan, pond, lonely*
- Golden Goose: *goose, gold, laughter, village, surprise*
- Peter Pan: *fairy, pirate, sword, island, fly*
- The Emperor's New Clothes: *emperor, cloth, invisible, tailor, parade*

I asked them to group these words into word classes.

After that, the students made story maps. I distributed medium-sized pieces of paper. They drew boxes according to the instructions, then filled them in according to their respective stories.

Then, after finishing, each group began presenting in front of the class. Group 2 went first, looking more confident than before. Group 2 began presenting the results of their group. The results of group 2 (*The Ugly Duckling*) were:

First, the results of the word class grouping

- Noun: *duckling, pond, swan, etc.*
- Verb: *swim, laugh, bully, etc.*
- Adjective: *ugly, lonely, beautiful, etc.*
- Adverb: *slowly, sadly, etc.*

After presenting the results of the word class grouping, group 2 immediately opened the medium-sized paper that had been prepared beforehand to write down the results of the Story Map, as follows:

- Characters: Mother duck, ugly duckling, other ducks, swan.
- Setting: Farm and pond.
- Problem: The duckling was bullied because he was different.
- Events: He felt lonely → He grew up → He met swans.
- Resolution: He became a beautiful swan.

When they gave their presentations, I saw that the students found it easier to explain the story because they were aided by the *story map* visualization. Group 5 confidently explained that "The emperor was fooled by the tailors, and the people laughed at him during the parade."

In this third meeting, I saw significant progress. The students were more fluent in finding the meaning of vocabulary, either through the dictionary or by asking me directly. With the *story map*, they seemed to understand the storyline more easily and were more confident during their presentations. Some groups even added small pictures to their story maps, such as a picture of a duck for *The Ugly Duckling* and a picture of a magic lamp for *Aladdin*.

In my opinion, the use of *story maps* is very beneficial because:

1. It makes the storyline easier to understand.
2. It helps students remember the structure of narrative texts.
3. It trains their skills in organizing information in an orderly manner.

I concluded the meeting by praising all the groups and emphasizing that the more often they create *story maps*, the easier it will be for them to understand *narrative texts* in the future.

Fourth Meeting

In the fourth meeting, I entered the classroom with enthusiasm because today the students would be given a new type of assignment, namely character analysis. After greeting them and engaging in a little small talk, I explained the purpose of the activity:

"Today you will read a new story, then analyze the characters in it. You will choose one main character, write down their traits, their role in the story, and evidence from the text that supports your opinion."

I kept the groups that had been assigned previously. Each group took turns coming forward to choose a book. In this meeting, the stories chosen were:

- Group 1 chose *Kancil and the Crocodiles*
- Group 2 chose *Timun Mas*
- Group 3 chose *Malin Kundang*
- Group 4 chose *The Lion and the Mouse*
- Group 5 chose *The Tortoise and the Hare*

There is only one hard copy of each title, so I immediately distributed soft copies to all group members so they could read simultaneously without having to wait for their turn.

I asked the students to read their stories carefully while writing down any new vocabulary they encountered. Some students opened their dictionaries to look up words such as *cunning*, *giant*, *curse*, *arrogant*, and *humble*. I also assisted them by answering questions about the meaning of words they did not know.

From my observations, each group managed to collect between 20 and 25 new vocabulary words. They then wrote these words in their notebooks and grouped them according to part of speech: noun, verb, adjective, and adverb.

After finishing reading, I gave more detailed instructions for the group assignment:

1. Choose the Main Character
 - For example: Kancil, Timun Mas, Malin Kundang, Lion, or Tortoise.
2. Analyze the Character
 - Discuss and write down in a simple table:
 - Name (Character Name)
 - Traits (Character Traits) → for example, clever, brave, selfish, kind, arrogant, patient
 - Role (Role in the Story) → protagonist, antagonist, supporting character
 - Evidence (Evidence from the Text) → quotes or events that demonstrate that trait
3. Group Discussion
 - All members give their opinions, then they write down the final results on the paper provided.
4. Presentation
 - Group 1 explains that Kancil is *clever but tricky*, as evidenced by the way he tricks the crocodile so he can cross the river.
 - Group 2 explains that Timun Mas is *brave and resourceful*, because she is able to fight giants with magical objects.
 - Group 3 explains that Malin Kundang is *arrogant and ungrateful*, as evidenced by his failure to recognize his mother.
 - Group 4 explained that Lion was initially *powerful but arrogant*, but later learned to be *kind and grateful* to Mouse.
 - Group 5 explained that Tortoise is *patient and consistent*, while Hare is *overconfident*, as evidenced by his defeat in the running race.

I explained to the students that this activity is beneficial for:

- Understanding the characters more deeply, not just the plot.
- Enriching vocabulary of adjectives such as *clever*, *arrogant*, *brave*, *humble*, *patient*.
- Practicing critical thinking by connecting character traits with evidence from the text.
- Encouraging group discussions so that they become accustomed to expressing and defending their opinions.

During the activity, I noticed that the students were enthusiastic because the stories they read were relatable and interesting. Group 1 even laughed while discussing Kancil's cleverness, while group 3 was quite serious because the story of Malin Kundang was full of moral messages. I feel that this task succeeded in making students not only understand the story, but also reflect on human traits through the characters. The students' enthusiasm seemed to increase, especially because the stories chosen varied from local fairy tales to international fables.

Fifth Meeting

That day was the last meeting of the treatment. I entered the classroom with mixed feelings, between happiness because I had reached the end of the series of activities, and also curiosity about the students' progress after the previous four meetings. As usual, 23 students were waiting, and the classroom atmosphere was quite warm because they had become accustomed to the routine of these activities.

After greeting them, I explained that today they would do Story Rewriting, which is rewriting the stories they had read with new versions based on their creativity. I emphasized that this task would help them understand narrative structure more deeply while training their imagination.

As usual, the students were divided into 5 groups according to the groups that had been assigned. Each group received one hard copy of the story, while I distributed the soft copy via the WhatsApp group so that all members could read it simultaneously without having to wait for their turn, given the limited number of printed books. Here are the books chosen by the 5 groups:

- Group 1: *Keong Mas (The Golden Snail)*
- Group 2: *The Monkey and the Crocodile*
- Group 3: *The Origin of Lake Toba*
- Group 4: *The Tale of the Crying Stone (Batu Menangis)*
- Group 5: *The Legend of Roro Jonggrang*

After choosing their books, the students immediately began reading. This time, they seemed more accustomed to the task. Some immediately took out their dictionaries without being told to, and some had already prepared their notebooks from the start. As I walked around, I saw the members of Group 4 starting to have a small discussion. They marked new vocabulary words that they did not understand, then wrote them down in their notebooks. The vocabulary words were then grouped into nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs.

On average, each group found 20–30 new vocabulary words. Some of the words that appeared were: *curse, palace, jealous, crocodile, sacrifice, grief, betray, collapse*.

If there are any difficult words, students can open the dictionary available on the teacher's desk or ask me directly.

After reading and noting down the vocabulary, I explain today's group task:

1. Discussion of the New Version of the Story
 - Students may change the ending of the story.
 - They can add new characters.
 - They can change the main character's personality.
2. Rewriting the Story
 - Written in 4–6 paragraphs using the narrative text structure (orientation – complication – resolution).
 - Must use at least 5 new vocabulary words that they have discovered.
3. Presenting the Results
 - Each group appoints a representative to read their new version of the story in front of the class.

Group Activity Results

- Group 1 rewrote *Keong Mas*, in which Keong Mas, after returning to human form, not only meets his mother, but also helps the people build a new kingdom.
- Group 2 created a version of *The Monkey and the Crocodile*, in which the crocodile finally realizes his mistake and befriends the monkey.
- Group 3 rewrote *The Origin of Lake Toba*, in which the lake was formed not because of a curse, but because of a father's sacrifice to protect his child.
- Group 4 changed *The Tale of Crying Stone*, in which the child finally realizes his mistake before completely turning into stone and regrets his actions.
- Group 5 rewrote *The Legend of Roro Jonggrang*, in which Roro Jonggrang is not cursed, but ends up working with Bandung Bondowoso to build a new kingdom.

I explained that this activity is beneficial for:

- Developing students' creativity through story modification.
- Deepening understanding of narrative structure through writing practice.
- Strengthening mastery of new vocabulary through its use in their own texts.
- Developing teamwork as each group must negotiate to determine the story idea.

During the activity, I saw that the students were enthusiastic. They had serious discussions but still laughed and joked, especially when unique ideas came up. During the presentations, some groups added humorous expressions, which livened up the classroom atmosphere. I considered this activity a successful and meaningful conclusion. The students not only understood the narrative text, but were also able to recreate the story with their own imagination. Then the class ended with a round of applause and words of thanks from the students. Some students even said that they would take the storybook home to read again. With smiles on their faces, the researcher realized that this extensive reading activity had instilled a habit that would likely continue to grow outside the classroom.

Post-test data description

The post-test is a test given to students by the researcher after the treatment has been carried out. This session was conducted after five treatments were given by the researcher in the classroom. The post-test results showed that the highest scores of the students were as follows:

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Graphic Polygon of the Post-test

The post-test polygon graph shows a very significant increase in students' vocabulary mastery after the learning treatment. The scores in all word classes showed high results, with nouns (160) being the category with the highest achievement, followed by verbs (158), adverbs (158), and adjectives (157). This pattern indicates that all students successfully achieved an even level of vocabulary mastery in all four word categories, with no students remaining at a low level. The concentration of scores in the high categories demonstrates the effectiveness of the " " learning strategy used, as it was able to increase not only the number of vocabulary words mastered by students but also the evenness of their ability to master various important word classes in English.

Table 2 Frequency Interval Data for Post-test Vocabulary

NO	INTERVAL CLASS	F ABSOLUTE	PERCENTAGE
1	21-23	2	9
2	24-25	3	13
3	26-27	4	17
4	28-29	6	26
5	30	8	35
Total		23	100%

Source: Processed Data (2025)

After applying the treatment through an extensive reading approach, the post-test score distribution showed a very significant increase compared to the pre-test. There were no longer any students in the low category. Two students (9%) scored in the 21–23 interval, and three students (13%) scored in the 24–25 interval. The number of students who achieved higher scores increased, with 4 students (17%) in the 26–27 interval and 6 students (26%) in the 28–29 interval. The highest achievement was shown by 8 students (35%) who managed to score 30, or a perfect score.

These results show that the majority of students (78%) achieved scores above 26, indicating a high level of vocabulary mastery. The distribution pattern concentrated in the upper categories proves that the learning approach used is effective in significantly and evenly improving students' vocabulary skills.

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Differences in Vocabulary Aspects on the Pre-Test and Post-Test

The comparison graph between the pre-test and post-test results shows a very significant increase in all word class categories. Nouns increased from a score of 97 to 160, indicating the highest jump in mastery. Verbs also showed a large increase, from 75 to 158. Meanwhile, adjectives, which were initially only 52, rose sharply to 157, and adverbs, which were originally at the lowest score of 39, increased dramatically to 158.

This comparison pattern shows that the post-test polygon line is consistently far above the pre-test line in all word class categories. This indicates that the learning treatment applied not only improved vocabulary in categories that students already relatively mastered, such as nouns and verbs, but also improved weaknesses in the adjective and adverb categories. Thus, the even improvement in the four word categories () reflects the success of the learning strategy in comprehensively strengthening students' vocabulary mastery.

Data Analysis Techniques

Normality Test

The Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test is a non-parametric statistical method designed to test hypotheses by comparing two related samples. This test is used when researchers want to know whether there is a significant difference between two paired data groups. Unlike parametric tests, the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test does not require the assumption of normal distribution, making it the right choice when the research data does not meet these criteria. Therefore, this method is often considered an alternative to the Paired Sample t-test, which is usually used when the data is normally distributed.

In practice, the Wilcoxon test is used to analyze the results of observations of two conditions taken from the same respondents, allowing researchers to directly evaluate the changes that occur after a particular treatment is given. The analysis is performed with the help of statistical software, such as SPSS version 20, which provides special facilities for running the Wilcoxon Test procedure. Mathematically, the calculation of this test can be described through a statistical formula that utilizes the difference in ranks between the two conditions being compared, resulting in a Z value as the basis for decision making regarding the research hypothesis.

Table 3

	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Negative Ranks	0		0.000
Positive Ranks	23	12,000	276,000
Ties	0		

Test Statistics

	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
POST-TEST VOCABULARY - PRE-TEST VOCABULARY	-4.197	0.000

Source: SPSS 23, Processed (2025)

Based on the data analysis in Table 4.3, the results of the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test show that all differences in scores between the pretest and posttest moved in a positive direction. This is reflected in the number of positive ranks, which was 23, with a mean rank of 12.00 and a total rank sum of 276.00. Meanwhile, there were no negative ranks or ties, which means that no students experienced a decrease in scores or maintained the same scores between the pretest and posttest.

Statistically, the test value produced was $Z = -4.197$ with a significance level of $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.001$). This value indicates that there was a very significant difference between the students' vocabulary scores on the pretest and posttest. In other words, the treatment or intervention given proved to be effective in improving students' vocabulary mastery.

Statistical Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing in this study requires a rational and logical approach to identify and determine the relationship between two or more variables. Hypothesis testing aims to evaluate whether the research results are as expected or not. Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted using a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

Based on the output results from IBM SPSS version 23, the criteria for hypothesis testing are as follows:

- 1) If the Sig. (2-tailed) value is < 0.05 , then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.
- 2) If the Sig. (2-tailed) value is > 0.05 , then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected.

DISCUSSION

The application of extensive reading-based learning in this study showed remarkable progress in students' vocabulary mastery, both in terms of understanding word types and their use in context. There were several differences and similarities between the conditions of the students before and after the treatment, as well as between the findings of this study and previous theories and studies.

Before the treatment was carried out, the majority of students showed limited and lexical vocabulary comprehension. They tended to recognize the meaning of words separately, without understanding the function of the word in a sentence. After undergoing five sessions of extensive reading-based learning, there was a significant change in the way students identified word classes (nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs), arranged them in sentences, and understood their meanings through the context of the story.

For example, previously, students tended to confuse words such as *cepat* and *cepat*, or *ajaib* and *ajaib*. However, after the treatment, they were able to distinguish the grammatical functions of each word and understand their contextual usage. This shows that learning not only increases the number of known vocabulary words, but also strengthens students' morphological and syntactic awareness.

This change confirms Krashen's view that exposure to comprehensible input through extensive reading activities will promote natural language acquisition. In addition, Nation's theory that vocabulary is more easily acquired through context is reflected in these findings, where students learn new words through the texts they read, rather than through explicit memorization.

Although each word class has its own challenges, there are similarities in the patterns of improvement in students' understanding of the four main categories of vocabulary: nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. All categories show progress in terms of word form recognition, function, and use in sentences.

All students showed improvement in their ability to connect the words they encountered in the text with the appropriate sentence structure. This was evident in the word classification and sentence construction activities they did in group discussions and individual assignments. These activities showed that vocabulary learning through extensive reading not only enriched vocabulary quantitatively but also deepened its functional understanding.

This supports Day and Bamford's theory that when students are given the freedom to choose reading materials according to their interests, they will be more engaged and able to absorb language comprehensively, including vocabulary.

Although there was an increase in all parts of speech, there were differences in the ease of mastery between categories. Nouns and verbs tended to be understood more quickly by students than adjectives and adverbs. Nouns and verbs are easier to associate with objects and actions in stories, while adjectives and adverbs, which are descriptive, require more abstract understanding.

These differences indicate that students need more practice and explicit guidance to understand the functions and nuances of adjectives and adverbs. This is in line with Endris' (2018) opinion, which emphasizes that the acquisition of abstract vocabulary requires contextual repetition and a deep understanding of meaning.

The findings in this study are similar to those of Ying & Yanting (2021), Rashidi & Piran (2021), and Shih (2020), all of which show that extensive reading can improve vocabulary mastery and reading comprehension. The students in this study not only discovered new vocabulary but were also able to use it actively in both spoken and written contexts.

As explained by Renandya & Jacobs, the extensive reading approach also contributed to a change in students' attitudes toward reading, from initially considering it boring to finding it enjoyable. This was also

evident in this study, where students began to show high enthusiasm for reading stories independently and noting down new vocabulary they encountered.

Research limitations

Based on the researchers' experience during the research process, there were several limitations and factors that could be considered for future research to improve this study, as this study itself certainly has shortcomings that need to be addressed in future research. Some of the limitations of this study include:

- Although the freedom to choose reading material is an advantage of extensive reading, it can be a disadvantage if students choose texts that are too easy (and therefore not challenging) or too difficult (and therefore frustrating). Without proper guidance, students may not get the maximum benefit.
- The limited number of respondents, only 23 people, meant that the results of this study could not represent a wider population. In other words, the results of this study cannot be generalized.
- Time constraints limited the research, resulting in a lack of in-depth exploration of the use of extensive reading and its implications for vocabulary use among students at SMP 12 GORONTALO.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that the application of extensive reading significantly improves the vocabulary mastery of seventh-grade students at SMP 12 Sipatana. This is evidenced by a significant difference in pretest and posttest scores based on the Paired Samples t-Test, with a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). The treatment provided through extensive reading activities, such as independent reading, recording new vocabulary, group discussions, and summary writing exercises, proved to be effective in enriching students' vocabulary.

Furthermore, this study supports previous findings that extensive reading provides exposure to vocabulary in various contexts, thereby helping students understand and remember new words. Thus, the extensive reading method can be an effective learning strategy () to improve students' reading skills and enrich their vocabulary, especially in English language learning. Therefore, it is recommended that this method be integrated into the school curriculum to support more effective and meaningful learning for students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the research conducted, several recommendations can be made by considering the following findings:

For Students

Students are expected to improve their independent reading habits by choosing reading materials that are interesting and appropriate for their level of understanding. In addition, students should familiarize themselves with new vocabulary and try to understand its meaning in various contexts to enrich their vocabulary more effectively.

For Teachers

Teachers can integrate extensive reading into the English language learning process by providing a variety of reading materials that are interesting and relevant to students' needs. In addition, teachers can provide guidance in understanding new vocabulary and create a learning environment that supports the development of students' reading skills.

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